

DYNAMICS OF AREA, PRODUCTION AND PRODUCTIVITY OF MILLETS IN INDIA

Manohar, B. H.^{1*}, Vijayakumar, J.S.² and Akshata Annasab Magadam³¹Assistant Professor (Contractual), Institute of Agribusiness Management, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bengaluru.²Ph. D. Scholar, ³M.Sc. (Agri), Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad

manoharhort4@gmail.com

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Abstract

India is the largest producer of millets in the world. Bajra and jowar together contributed around 19 per cent of world's production. Rajasthan, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana and Gujarat together accounted for more than 83 per cent share in total millet production in India. Rajasthan alone contributes around 28.61 per cent of millets production in India. Therefore the present study aimed to analyze the growth and dynamics of cereals and millets production in India. The study was based on secondary data which was collected from different public sources especially Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), Cuddy-Della Valle Index and Markov chain analysis was adopted for analysis of data. The results revealed that the negative growth had been observed in area of millets in India. Whereas, positive growth was noticed in production and productivity of millets in India and the data is stable during the study period. The coarse cereals, small millets and bajra are the crops retained their area in India during the study period. At the same period ragi lost cent per cent of its area to wheat. It could be concluded that there is a potential to grow the cereals and millets in India.

Keywords: Cereals, Millets, Compound Annual Growth Rate, Cuddy -Della Valle index, markov chain

Introduction

Millets are resilient, small-seeded grasses group of cereal or grains grown for fodder and human consumption. Millets grow in adaptive to a wide range of ecological conditions and thrive well in rain-fed and arid climate. These properties of millets make them agriculturally superior to other commercial crops. They have nutritional superiority over other cereals for its micronutrient profile and bioactive flavonoids which makes them highly valuable. The high protein content of these grains makes them ideal for vegetarian population largely based in the U.S., Europe and Asia Pacific. Millets especially pearl millet and lesser millets are cultivated in over 93 countries throughout the world. Sorghum is the called "King of Millets" and most frequently grown millet with 42.1 million hectares in 105 countries. In developing countries, particularly in Africa and Asia they produce and consume 97 per cent of millets and contributing to 26.6 percent of the world's millet growing area out of which Asia covers 83 percent of millet growing area. India is the world's largest producer of millets with share of around 41 per cent with the production of around 1,24,90,000 tonnes followed by Niger (35,08,903 tonnes), China (23,00,499 tonnes), Nigeria (20,00,000 tonnes) and Mali (19,21,171 tonnes) during the year 2020-21. Globally the demand for nutria-cereals rising steadily around three per cent of Compound Annual Growth Rate in the last five years (Anonymous, 2020a).

Globally, the major exporter of millets are USA, Russian Federation, Ukraine, India, China, Netherlands, France, Poland and Argentina altogether exported nearly USD 221.68 million during 2020. Global exports of millets during 2020 were USD 466.284 million and India is the fifth largest exporter of millets worth USD 26.97 million. The top three importers of millets from India in 2020-21 were Nepal (USD 6.09 million), UAE (USD 4.84 million) and Saudi Arabia (USD 3.84 million) respectively. During 2020, the major importing countries of millets with their share in world's import are Indonesia (8%), Belgium (7.36%), Germany (4.65), Mexico (4.1%), Italy (4.02%), United States of America (3.35%), United Kingdom (3.25%) Brazil (3.24%) and Netherlands (3.14%), these top ten importers together accounted for USD 221.7 million. In India, the top five major millets producing states were Rajasthan (46.33 Lakh tonnes), Maharashtra (23.58 Lakh tonnes), Karnataka (23.19 Lakh tonnes), Uttar Pradesh (20.755 Lakh tonnes) and Madhya Pradesh (10.83 Lakh tonnes). With this huge production in India and export potentiality of the millets the present study conducted with the objective to evaluate the growth in area, production and productivity in India over the years and to know the behavior of direction of trade in International market (Anonymous, 2020b).

Methodology

The study purely based on secondary data pertaining to the millets area, production and productivity which were collected from Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India from 2010-11 to 2020-21 over the period of eleven years. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) technique was adopted to estimate the growth in area, production and productivity of millets in India and Markov chain analysis was employed to analyze the structural change in area of millets whose progress through time can be measured in terms of single outcome variable over the years.

Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR)

In order to analyze the growth rate in area, production and productivity of millets compound annual growth rate and to know the variations in area, production and productivity of millets, instability index was computed using the following model.

$$Y_t = ab^t e^u$$

Where,

Y_t = dependent variable (area or production or productivity of millets in India)

a = intercept term

$b = (1+r)$ and ' r ' is the compound growth rate

t = time period

u = error term

The above model in the Logarithmic form is expressed as, $\log Y = \log a + t \log b + \log u$

Thus the Compound Annual Growth Rate (r) could be calculated as follows

$$CAGR(r) = (\text{Antilog of } \log b - 1) \times 100$$

Where,

r = Compound growth rate per annum in per cent,

The coefficient of variation (CV) was used as the measure of instability as under:

$$CV\% = \frac{\text{Standard deviation (sd)}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$$

Cuddy-Della Valle index

Cuddy Della Valle Instability index is a modification of coefficient of variation to accommodate trend present in the data, which is commonly present in economic time series data. This method is superior over the scale dependent measures such as standard deviation. The Cuddy Della Valle index (CDVI) is calculated as follows:

$$CDVI = CV *$$

Where, $X=1-R^2$, CV is coefficient of variation and R^2 is adjusted

$$E_{jt} = \sum_{i=1}^r E_{it-1} P_{ij} + e_{jt}$$

coefficient of determination. The ranges of CDVI (Das *et al.*, 2019) are given as follows:

Low instability = between 0 and 15

Medium instability = greater than 15 and lower than 30

High instability = greater than 30

Markov chain analysis

Markov chain analysis was employed to analyze the structural change in any system whose progress through time can be measured in terms of single outcome variable. In the present study, the dynamic nature of trade patterns of cereals from India studied using the Markov chain model. Markov chain analysis involving developing a transitional probability matrix 'P', whose elements, P_{ij} indicate the probability of exports switching from country 'i' to country 'j' over time. The diagonal element P_{ij} where $i=j$, measure the probability of a country retaining its market share or in other words, the loyalty of an importing country to a particular country's exports. In the context of current application, structural change was treated as a random process with eight importing countries for cereals. The assumption was that the average export of cereals from a country amongst importing countries in any period depends only on the export in the previous period and this dependence is same for all the periods. This was algebraically expressed as

Where,

E_{jt} = Shifts in area of one millet in India to the j^{th} millet in the year t

E_{it-1} = Area of i^{th} millet during the year t-1

P_{ij} = Probability that area will shift from i^{th} millet to j^{th} millet

e_{jt} = the error term which is statistically independent of E_{it-1}

n = the number of millets

The transitional probabilities P_{ij} , which can be arranged in a $(c \times r)$ matrix, have the following properties.

$0 < P_{ij} < 1 = 1$ for all i

Thus, the expected shifts in area of each millets during period 't' is obtained by multiplying the shifts in area of other millets in the previous period (t-1) with the transitional probability matrix. The

Table 1. Growth and instability index in area, production and productivity of cereals and millets in India

Year	Area ('000 Ha)	Production ('000 Tonnes)	Productivity (Kg/Ha)
2010-11	1,00,270	2,26,241	2256
2011-12	1,00,293	2,42,197	2415
2012-13	97,514	2,38,792	2449
2013-14	99,829	2,45,790	2462
2014-15	1,00,746	2,34,871	2331
2015-16	98,306	2,35,218	2393
2016-17	99,786	2,51,981	2525
2017-18	97,711	2,59,597	2657
2018-19	95,621	2,63,133	2752
2019-20	99,007	2,74,479	2772
2020-21	1,01,012	2,85,279	2824
CAGR (%)	-0.11	1.96***	2.07***
R²	0.051	0.81	0.82
CV	0.017	0.068	0.070
CDVI (%)	1.67	3.00	2.99

Source: Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, Govt. of India.

Note: *** indicates significant at 1 per cent.

This conveyed that the time series data for area, production and productivity during the study period is stable.

Transition probability matrix for shifts in area of cereals and millets in India

The dynamics of shifts in area of cereals and millets in India were computed using transitional probability matrix which is deliberated

probability matrices were estimated for the period from 2010-11 to 2021-22. Thus, transitional probability matrix (T) was estimated using linear programming (LP) frame work by a method referred to as minimizing of Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD).

Min, $O P^* + I e$

Subject to $X P^* + V = YGP^* =$

1

$P^* > 0$

Where,

P^* is a vector of the probabilities P_{ij} ; O is

the vector of zeros

i is an appropriately dimensional vectors of areas e is the vector of absolute errors

Y is the proportion of shifts in area of one millet to other

X is a block diagonal matrix of lagged values of YV is

the vector of errors

G is a grouping matrix to add the row elements of P arranged in P^* to unity.

The values in the transition probability matrix will have different interpretations. The value of diagonal elements indicates the probability of retention of the previous year's share, while values in the columns reveal probability of gain by a particular country from other countries, values in rows reveal probability that a country might lose to other countries in respect of a specific commodity exports.

Results and Discussion

The growth and instability index in area, production and productivity of combined cereals and millets in India are presented in Table 1. The data was collected and analyzed for the period of 11 years. The results revealed that, the area showed the negative growth during the study period (-0.11%) which is showing non-significant. But, production and productivity was in positive growth of 1.96 per cent and 2.07 per cent respectively in which both are significant at 1 per cent level of significance. This increase in growth of production and productivity might be due to introduction of high yielding varieties or due to adoption of different technologies in enhancement of productivity. The CDVI index revealed that in terms of area, productions as well as productivity the lower instability have been observed in the study over the period of time wherein the CDVI for area was 1.67 per cent, production 3 per cent and for productivity it was 2.99 per cent.

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Transition probability matrix for shifts in area of cereals and millets in India

The dynamics of shifts in area of cereals and millets in India were computed using transitional probability matrix which is deliberated

in Table 2. The major cereals and millets were bajra, barley, coarse cereals, jowar, maize, ragi, small millets, wheat and the remaining items are categorized as others. The results revealed that bajra retained around 42.56 per cent of area in India during 2010-2021 (12

years). Bajra gained from coarse cereals (12.82%), wheat (0.53%) and others (5.35%) at the same time it lost its area to ragi, small millets and others which is around 0.64 per cent, 1.03 per cent and 55.78 per cent respectively. Barley not retained its area during the study period. It lost its share in area of 50.23 per cent to jowar, 38.51 per cent to ragi and 11.26 per cent to others and gained 34.52 per cent

from small millets, 1.02 per cent from wheat and 0.54 percent from other crops. Coarse cereals retained around 69.88 per cent of its area and lost its area to bajra (12.82%), jowar (6.83%), ragi (0.08%), 10.39 per cent to wheat at the same time it gained from jowar (33.89%) and others (28.30%).

Table 2. Transition probability matrix for shifts in area of cereals and millets in India for the period from 2010 to 2021

Crop		LOSS								
		Bajra	Barley	Coarse cereals	Jowar	Maize	Ragi	Small Millets	Wheat	Others
GAIN	Bajra	0.4256	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0064	0.0103	0.5578	0.0000
	Barley	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.5023	0.0000	0.3851	0.0000	0.0000	0.1126
	Coarse cereals	0.1282	0.0000	0.6988	0.0683	0.0000	0.0008	0.0000	0.1039	0.0000
	Jowar	0.0000	0.0000	0.3389	0.3286	0.0000	0.0000	0.0396	0.2929	0.0000
	Maize	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0579	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.9421
	Ragi	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	0.0000
	Small Millets	0.0000	0.3452	0.0000	0.1004	0.0000	0.0989	0.4555	0.0000	0.0000
	Wheat	0.0053	0.0102	0.0000	0.0500	0.2611	0.0254	0.0000	0.3743	0.2737
	Others	0.0535	0.0054	0.2830	0.0000	0.0482	0.0000	0.0000	0.4979	0.1121

Similarly, jowar retained around 32.86 per cent of its area and it lost its area to coarse cereals, small millets, wheat of 33.89 per cent, 3.96 per cent and 29.29 per cent respectively. Jowar gained its area from barley (50.23%), coarse cereals (6.83%), small millets (10.04%) and wheat (5%). Maize crop retained 5.79 per cent of its area where in lost its maximum area of 94.21 per cent to other and simultaneously gained 26.11 per cent from wheat and 4.82 per cent from others. Ragi crop lost its whole area to wheat which is around cent per cent. The probable reason for shifts of ragi producer to wheat producer might be the farmers produced export-oriented wheat and might have exported to foreign countries. While, it gained from bajra (0.64%), barley (38.51%), coarse cereals (0.08%), small millets (9.89%) and wheat (2.54%). Small millets retained 45.55 per cent of its area and gained 3.96 per cent from jowar and 1.03 per cent from bajra. Small millets lost its area to barley (34.52%), jowar (10.04%) and ragi (9.89%). Wheat retained around 37.43 per cent of its area during the study period. It lost its area to bajra (0.53%), barley (1.02%), jowar (5%), maize (26.11%), ragi (2.54%) and others (27.37%). Wheat gained maximum area from ragi (100%), others (49.79%), jowar (29.29%), coarse cereals (10.39%) and bajra (55.78%). Around 11.12 per cent of area had been retained and maximum of 94.21 per cent of area was gained from maize and 49.79 per cent area lost to wheat. These results revealed that in India due to diversified climatic conditions the different types of crops could be grown in the country. This lead to huge production of cereals and millets in India. The farmers are eager to enrich the returns therefore; they were involved in changing cropping pattern with in the cereals and millets to gain higher returns based on the crop plan and market situation.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the area of millets and cereals in India was in negative trend. Whereas, production and productivity were showed the positive trend wherein the significant constant growth had been noticed during the study period. The results revealed that coarse cereals, small millets and bajra are the cereals and millets are reliable in their area. Therefore, it could be concluded that there is a potential to grow the cereals and millets in India.

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